

Clews-Based Comparative Analysis for Power Sector and Land Use Change Scenarios in Ghana

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study examines the effects of applying an integrated systems approach, with an emphasis on energy and land systems in Ghana. Three scenarios were developed —the Base Case Scenario, the Built-up Land Scenario, and the Renewable Energy Target Scenario – which were created through modelling exercises using the CLEWs framework and OSeMOSYS tool.

Findings from the base case scenario reveal that the renewable energy (solar, wind) and nuclear power sources added in the modelling were not shown as part of the power-producing technologies through the modelling years after the model run. However, when the renewable energy target was implemented, it forced investment in renewable energy power plants resulting in a reduction in CO₂ emission, and water demand for power generation. Also increasing land for built-up areas led to reduced agricultural land and a slight increase in the demand for public water supply.

Recommendations include a policy that halts the land for built-up areas by 2050 to conserve the lands for forests which would serve as a carbon sink. Land use policies that balance the need for built-up areas with the preservation of land for renewable energy projects should be developed and enforced. Also, the study recommends policies that incentivize the adoption and integration of renewable energy technologies, such as solar and wind, into the national grid. This could include subsidies, tax incentives, or feed-in tariffs to make renewable energy more attractive to investors and developers.

INTRODUCTION

Ghana submitted its first NDC in 2015 and updated NDC in 2021. Under the updated NDC, Ghana aims to implement nine unconditional actions that would result in 8.5 MtCO₂e emissions reductions by 2025 and a further reduction of 24.6 MtCO₂e by 2030 (Ghana Updated NDC, 2021). The Renewable Energy Act aims for the country to achieve 10 % renewable energy penetration by the year 2030 (Aboagye *et al.*, 2021). This target is again captured in Ghana's National Energy Transition Framework (2022-2070), with another RE target layer of 20% by 2070.

The country currently has a renewable energy penetration of 2.8%. The scope of the study is to perform a comparative analysis of three scenarios – Base Case, Renewable Energy Target, and Built-up Land applying the CLEWs framework using the OSeMOSYS tool.

The main goal is to comprehend how Ghana's power technology transitions' viewpoint is changed by the implementation of an integrated systems approach. Additionally, this research seeks to assess how the political ambition of achieving net zero through the introduction of RE into the power generation sector would impact other sectors in the nexus. Finally, it seeks to offer insights and recommendations to stakeholders in the energy sector as well as policymakers.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) framework was applied using the OSeMOSYS (Open-Source Energy Modelling System) tool. It provides a platform for developing and studying scenarios relating to the CLEWs nexus. It enables users or modelers to explore the various implications of different policies and investment decisions. Fig. 1 summarizes the key assumptions of the scenarios.

Fig. 1 Summary of Scenarios' Key Assumptions

The CLEWs modeling methodology allowed for an analysis of technology-specific challenges and their implications for energy policy decision-making. In the Base case scenario, data were obtained from the starter data kit (CCG Starter Data Kits, 2020). For Ghana, we generated a hypothetical reference energy system for the country. In addition, land cover and water data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) database. In modelling the Renewable Energy Target scenario, the assumptions were based on the current trajectory of the renewable energy share of the country's energy mix. Currently, the country has a 2.8% renewable energy penetration in the energy mix with the projection of a 10 % increase by the year 2030 and by 20 % in 2070 (Ghana National Energy Transition framework). The land scenario assumes a 7 % increase per year in the build-up areas over the modelling period due to a projected increase in the country's population growth.

RESULTS

Results revealed variations across the three scenarios: Base, Renewable Energy Target, and Land Cover Scenario with each shedding light on critical points.

- In the **Base case** scenario, coal and natural gas emerged as the major power-producing technologies, with hydro being the minimum. This can be attributed to the capital cost and the availability of resources. For the land use, the total available land was split among the land use for agriculture, forest, water, and other uses comprising bare lands among others.
- For the **Renewable energy target** scenario, it was evident that renewable energy power-producing technologies mainly solar and wind emerged as a part of the energy mix in contrast to that of the base. From 2020-2024, the current penetration rate of 2.8% was used and then shared in a ratio of 7:3 for solar and wind respectively, increasing to 10% by 2030 and 20 % by 2070
- For the **Land Cover Scenario**, the built-up area, was increased by 7% per annum over the model period. This increase reduced the agricultural land and increased the public water supply.

Fig. 2 depicts the base case scenario. On the left, is the power generation capacity in gigawatts, and on the right is the power generation detail in petajoules. In the base scenario, the major power-producing

technologies are from fossil fuels and a small portion from hydro. This resulted in a high demand for water to cool the thermal power plants.

Fig. 2. Installed Power Generation Capacity and Electricity Generation

The Renewable Energy scenario showed a progressive transition towards renewable energy sources as contained in the Ghana National Energy Transition Framework (2022 – 2070). The results of this scenario showed a reduction in CO₂ emissions and water demand for power generation (figure 4 and figure 5 respectively) This highlights the need to ensure a balance between transitioning to low-emission power sources and managing water resources sustainably.

Base Case Power Generation Capacity

RE Scenario Power Generation Capacity

Fig. 3 Comparative Analysis of the Base Case and Renewable Energy Target in terms of Capacity

Fig. 4 Comparison of Annual Emissions for the Base Case and Renewable Energy Target Scenarios

Fig. 5 Comparative Analysis of Power Sector Water Demand for the Base Case and RE Target Scenarios

The **Built-up land** scenario presents the impact of increasing land for built-up areas on the overall land cover attribution. For this scenario, the built-up land was increased by 7% per annum. This had a clear impact on the land for forests and agriculture (Fig. 6) which will have to compensate for the area to be cleared for the built environment.

Fig. 6 Comparison of the Base Case and Land Cover Change Scenarios

DISCUSSION

The insights from this model were very informative as it shows the various implications of how a change in one aspect of a CLEW system can impact others. In the RE scenario, the renewable energy technologies addition to the energy mix greatly reduced the capacity of fossil fuel-based power plants which as a result reduced the carbon dioxide emissions and water demand for the power sector.

Based on this modeling exercise, the policy recommendation is for the Ghanaian government to increase its share of renewable energy penetration to the set target of the National Energy Transition Framework. This will greatly shift the energy mix from fossil fuel-based plants to that of cleaner energy lower emissions towards the achievement of net zero emissions by 2070.

It is important to realize that renewable energies would not emerge as cost-effective power generation systems, as was shown in the base case scenario unless a deliberate effort is made to promote these technologies. If the policies and instruments in the Renewable Energy Act of the country are followed to the latter, it will help increase the rate of adoption of the technology.

Another policy recommendation would be to set a target to restrict the expansion of the built-up environment. This is for the country to conserve the land for forests as a carbon sink to reduce the effects of emissions. This built-up area in this discussion includes land areas for residential, industrial commercial, and renewable power plant construction, etc.

The limitations that applied to the modelling exercise were that it relied partially on the reference systems made up of the present and future energy systems of the country. This means that while it is insightful, it does not represent fully, the current energy system for Ghana. Using the data available on the ground and their respective capacities will aid future modelers in making informed decisions on the current implications of the system.

Potential areas for future research include modelling the decline of natural gas in the energy mix by the mid-2050s and the introduction of nuclear power in the energy mix as contained in Ghana's National Energy Transition Framework

CONCLUSION

Through the analysis of three scenarios, the base, renewable energy target, and built-up land, this study has provided valuable insights on the current situation for Ghana and also projections on how making decisions on the components of the CLEWS affects the nexus as a whole. The base case was not placed under any constraint, unlike the other scenarios to set a benchmark for the other scenarios to be compared to.

In the base case scenario, it was shown that the Osemosys model gives priority to the technologies that have lower capital costs and higher availability. This made fossil-fuel-powered plants become the largest in the energy mix. In the renewable energy scenario, the solar and wind power plants were forced online with the help of the Total Technology Annual Activity Lower Limit parameter. Afterward, it was shown to have had a huge impact on the reduction of the emissions associated with the power sector. In the land aspect, the increase in built-up land had reduced forest land. Moving forward, Ghana should take into consideration the nexus, in policy-making as changes in one of the nexus could significantly impact others

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